

Thermal Energy Storage Systems for Energy Efficient Buildings

TESSe2b tests prototypes in Austria, Spain and Cyprus

European project will be test in different
climate conditions

Austria, Region of Graz

The house is located in Kapfenberg, 40 km north of Graz. The current oil based heating system and DWH system will be replaced by the TESSe2b system, using a ground sourced heat pump, solar collectors, PCM-based heat and cool storage and a smart control system.

Spain, Region of Barcelona

The house is located in Calonge de Segarra, 100 km from Barcelona. This will be the first demosite to be built and it will have the new TESSe2b system for heating and cooling and for domestic hot water.

Cyprus, Region of Pafos

The house is located in Meliou village, 35 km from Pafos town airport and 14 km from the Latchi beach area. Although it has 28 years old it is in good condition. The heating and cooling system and DWH system will be improved with the TESSe2b system.

The first **TESSe2b workshop and B2B meeting** took place at Ruhr University Bochum, Germany, at 22 June 2017. It's results will help to shape the project's goals in line with the market requirements.

Visit our website and find out more information about this innovative project.

[visit website](#)

